

Quantum Free Particle $\exp(ipx)$ With p Being Dynamic and x Static

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The quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ involves the dynamic variable p (which is directly linked to velocity v). The variable x may at first glance appear to be dynamic because $x=vt$, but we argue that it is not. If it were, one could rewrite $\exp(ipx)$ as $\exp(i pvt)$. The problem with this interpretation is that the one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon cannot be solved using continuity of $\exp(i pvt)$ and its first derivative d/dt , while it can be solved using continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative. This suggests that x is a static variable even though p is dynamic.

This, we argue, is in keeping with ideas in previous notes suggesting that $\exp(ipx)$ follows from $P(x)=1/L$. Here $P(x)$ is a classical probability, but x is not dynamic - it is not tied to time. $P(x)=1/L$ holds for all constant velocities. We suggested that $P(x)=Pd(x,p)P(x,-p)$, i.e. that in order to remove dynamics one must have p and $-p$ together. In this case, p is dynamic, but x is not. Thus, one cannot simply replace x with vt in $\exp(ipx)$.

This may at first lead to a seeming contradiction in Fermat's Least Time Principle applied to the two dimensional refraction of light. In such a case, one wishes to minimize time, but using the dynamic distance= vt to rewrite time in terms of Y,x . One then takes d/dx and finds that $p(x$ component in $n_1) = p$ (x component in n_2) where n_1 and n_2 are two different indices of refraction and the junction is the line $y=0$. One may argue that d/dx of $p(x$ component) x also yields p (x component). In the x -direction it is as if $\exp(ipx)$ is continuous, but this continuity holds for any x point solution of the Fermat's Least Time principle, i.e. one may shine the incident beam so it hits any x point. Thus, in the $\exp(ipx)$ case, x is a static, not a dynamic variable, whereas in the Fermat's least time principle x is dynamic, although both lead to conservation of momentum in the x direction.

Quantum Free Particle Wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ and Possible Problem

The quantum free particle wavefunction is $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$, with $\exp(ipx)$ being the spatial part. If one considers a one dimensional photon reflection problem, with an n_1 - n_2 interface occurring at $x=0$ (n =index of refraction), this problem may be solved by demanding continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s and their first derivative at $x=0$. In particular:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((1a)) \text{ and}$$

$$A p \exp(ipx) - B p \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((1b))$$

Note: E is the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photon.

Here A is a weight linked to the incident photon, B to the reflected and C to the refracted. This leads to: $AAp - BBp = CC p_2$ ((2)). Using $E=pc$, one has $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2$. Thus, AA may be interested as a flux and AA/c the number of incident particles. If $AA=1$, then BB/c and CC/c_2 are probabilities for reflection and refraction.

An apparent problem arises if one uses:

$$x=vt \quad (3)$$

$$\text{i.e. } \exp(ipx) = \exp(ipvt) \quad (4)$$

One might argue that $p_v = (-p)(-v)$ so that ((4)) does not distinguish between p and $-p$, but it does in the sense that if the incident photon reaches the junction at $t=0$, then before it is in negative time, while the reflected one is in positive time. The real problem, however, is that if one insists on continuity of $\exp(ipvt)$ at $t=0$ and also continuity of the first derivative d/dt , then:

$$A \exp(ipvt) = B \exp(ipvt) + C \exp(ip_2v_2t) \quad \text{at } t=0 \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$A p_v \exp(ipvt) = B p_v \exp(ipvt) + C p_2v_2 \exp(ip_2v_2t) \quad \text{at } t=0 \quad ((4b))$$

First of all, $A=B+C$ contradicts ((1a)) and secondly $p_c=E$ and E is the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photon so ((4a)) and ((4b)) are the same equation. One requires two equations if A is assumed to be 1, so $\exp(ipvt)$ continuity (with first derivative) does not solve the problem. This suggests that $\exp(ipx)$ is fine, but $\exp(ipvt)$ is not.

We argue that a mistake must have been made by writing $\exp(ipx) = \exp(ipvt)$, but $x=vt$ is correct. We suggest that in $\exp(ipx)$, p is dynamic, but x is not. As a result, using $x=vt$ treats x as a dynamic variable which is not allowed. Setting $x=0$ as the junction point is fine because this junction exists even without the photon being present. Using $\exp(ipvt)$ and $x=vt$ suggests that the photon must reach the junction at $t=0$. This is a dynamical statement whereas $x=0$ is not. The $\exp(ipx)$ probability approach, we argue, means there is uncertainty in space and one cannot really know exactly when the photon reaches the target (within the last wavelength). On average the photon does travel as $x=vt$.

We next consider arguments made in previous notes when deriving $\exp(ipx)$ to show that x is static, not dynamic.

Derivation of $\exp(ipx)$ from $P(x)=1/L$

The classical probability $P(x)dx = 1/L dx$ for a particle with a constant velocity. The more general form is $P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x)$ where $.5m v(v)v(x) + V(x) = E$ (nonrelativistic).

In $P(x)$, x is a static, not a dynamic variable and p or v do not appear at all. "X" represents space at no particular time. P and v are clearly dynamic variables. We argued in previous notes that for each $p, -p$ pair:

$$P(x) = 1/L = P_d(px) P_d(-px) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } P_d(px) \text{ is a dynamical probability}$$

$P_d(px)$ is dynamical because of p not x . X is static as it is in $P(x)$ and so one cannot use $x=vt$ and set $\exp(ipx) = \exp(ipvt)$ and use continuity of the latter.

Fermat's Least Time Principle and the Use of distance=vt

Fermat's Least Time Principle for two dimensional photon refraction minimizes time, but uses distance = v t, with distance being a function of y (initial)=Y x(initial)=0 and x which is the unknown x point at which the photon hits the n1-n2 interface which lies at y=0. This leads to the following form:

$$d/dx F(x) = d/dx F(L-x) \rightarrow p(x \text{ component in } n1) = p(x \text{ component in } n2) \quad ((6))$$

In particular: $t=x/c$ and $F(x) = \text{sqrt}(YY + xx)/c$ and $E=p1c = p2c$

((6)) is conservation of momentum in the x direction, but it is obtained by using distance=vt to replace time with F(x,L) and then taking d/dx of time(x) and setting it equal to 0 to minimize time taken. In this case, distance(x,L)=vt is a dynamic equation, but x is also a dynamic point because one assumes that one does not know the x point at which the photon strikes the n1-n2 interface which is at y=0.

We suggested in previous notes that one could define a different function $G= p(x \text{ component}) x$ so that $d/dx G = p$ just as in ((6)). In this case, however, x is simply a space variable. No dynamics are implied. Thus, simply because x appears does not mean that it is the dynamic variable indicated by $x=vt$. Probability(x) is a static concept, i.e. $P(x)=1/L$ does not change in time and so x is not a variable which follows the motion of a particle in time as $x=vt$ does.

Conclusion

In conclusion, even though the free particle wavefunction is $\exp(ipx)$ and $x=vt$ on average, we argue that one cannot simply substitute $\exp(ipx)=\exp(ipv t)$. In particular, the continuity of $\exp(ipvt)$ and its first derivative d/dt at $t=0$ break down for a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem while they do not break down for $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that x is a static variable and so cannot be replaced with $x=vt$ which is dynamic. If $x=0$ represents the n1-n2 junction (n=index of refraction), this is set even without a photon, but $x=0=vt \rightarrow t=0$ means that a photon reaches the junction at $t=0$. "t" is thus a dynamic variable which changes the whole meaning of the probability $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, we suggest that one cannot replace x with vt.

To see this another way, we suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the classical probability $P(x)dx=dx/L$. In this case, x is a position in space, i.e. a static variable as expected. There is no time associated with x. $P(x)=1/L$ applies to all p and v values, either to the right or left. We suggest that for a given p, one must assume that: $P(x)=1/L = Pd(px)Pd(-px)$. This yields $Pd(px)=\exp(ipx)$ which we call a dynamic probability, but only because p and not x is dynamic. X in $\exp(ipx)$ must be static as x in $P(x)$ is. Therefore, one cannot simply replace x with vt in $\exp(ipx)$.

We finally consider Fermat's Least time principle which uses distance= vt to replace time. distance= $\sqrt{YY + xx}$ in n_1 and $\sqrt{YY + (x-L)(x-L)}$ in n_2 . Taking d/dx of the sum and setting to 0 yields $p(x \text{ component in } n_1) = p(x \text{ component in } n_2)$. We suggested in previous notes that one may take a different function: $p(x \text{ component}) x$ such that d/dx yields $p(x \text{ component})$. In the Fermat's Least Time Principle, x is a dynamic variable. It represents the x point at which the photon hits the n_1 - n_2 interface. In $p(x \text{ component}) x$, it is a static variable (not dynamic) which represents x space. Thus, one cannot replace it with a dynamic function of time, we argue.